

***IN VITRO* ANTI-OXIDANT AND *IN VIVO* ANTI DIABETIC ACTIVITY
OF METHANOLIC LEAF EXTRACT OF *HELICTERES ISORA***

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ABSTRACT

The folkloric claims that *Helicteres isora* confers anti diabetic effect to prescribed patients has received long term clinical application accompanied by limited scientific data in support of such claims. Oxidative stress plays a major role in diabetic physiopathology; hence, the interest of using natural antioxidants as therapeutic tools exists. This study aimed for anti-oxidant and hypoglycemic activity of the methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora* in alloxan induced diabetic rats. Diabetes mellitus was induced in rats by intraperitoneal administration of alloxan monohydrate followed by graded doses of the methanolic leaf extract administered to the diabetic rats following an overnight fast. *In vitro* anti-oxidant was performed by DPPH free radical scavenging activity, Nitric oxide (NO) free radical scavenging method, and reducing power method (RP); the composition of the various phytochemicals of the plant extract was quantitatively assessed using standard procedures. Oral administration of the methanolic leaf extract caused a significant reduction in plasma glucose level in a dose independent manner. The hypoglycemic activity could be attributed to phytoconstituents found in the plant extract. The generated data supports the folkloric claims associating *Helicteres isora* with hypoglycemic effects. However, there is need for further studies on this plant to investigate the mechanism of its activity and determine its safety profiles in order to explore possibilities of developing a new anti-diabetic drug

Key words: *Helicteres isora*, Diabetes mellitus, alloxan, anti-oxidant, DPPH free radical scavenging activity

INTRODUCTION

Traditional herbal medicines have shaped the basis of human health care, and further research will improve global health [1, 2]. Presently, about 80% of the world population (according to WHO) uses herbal drugs for some aspects of primary health care. Globally, the use of medicinal plants predates antibiotics and other contemporary drugs [3, 4]. In addition, many culinary herbs and spices were tested for their biological activities in Alzheimer's disease management and other chronic diseases [5, 6].

The natural antioxidant defence mechanism, in all human and other aerobic organisms, prevents the oxidative damage. Since the natural antioxidant defence mechanism is inadequate on its own, the nutritional consumption of antioxidants is suggested [7, 8]. Currently, synthetic antioxidants are replaced by natural antioxidants as the former are reported to have carcinogenic properties. Plants are the primary source of natural antioxidant molecules capable of eliminating or neutralizing the harmful reactive oxygen species (ROS) [9]. The natural antioxidants are also free-radical scavengers, reduction agents, pro-oxidant metal complexes, singlet oxygen quenchers, etc. They can also safeguard the human body from free radicals and delay the progression of many chronic illnesses (such as cancer, heart disease, and stroke) and boost the plasma's antioxidant ability and prevent lipid oxidative rancidity in foods [10].

The incidence of diabetes mellitus (DM) is very high all over the world. Natural anti diabetic drugs are now becoming increasingly popular due to severe financial burdens and side effects connected with allopathic therapy strategies. The herbal preparations are complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) and the search for the discovery of novel compounds derived from natural sources like herbs or plant is growing mainly due to acquired resistance, side effects, and adverse events (AE) of allopathic medication.

Helicteres isora, sometimes called the Indian screw tree, is a small tree or large shrub found in southern Asia and northern Oceania. It is usually assigned to the family *Malvaceae*, [11] but it is sometimes assigned to the family *Sterculiaceae*. [12] The red flowers are pollinated mainly by sunbirds, butterflies, and Hymenoptera. In the 19th century fibers from the bark were used to make rope and sacks, although nowadays the tree is harvested for the fruits and roots which are used in folk medicine.

The present study was investigating the *in vitro* anti-oxidant and *in vivo* anti diabetic activity of methanolic leaf extract of *Helicteres isora*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material- collection and authentication

The leaves of *Helicteres isora* were collected from native species growing in deciduous forests of Tirumala region, Andhra Pradesh, India. The leaves have been identified taxonomically and authenticated by Dr. S. Madhava Chetty, Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Preparation of the extracts

The collected leaves were washed thoroughly with water and dried in the shade at room temperature. The dried leaves were ground well to coarse powder (400gms). Methanolic extract was obtained by extracting powder with methanol using Soxhlet apparatus by continuous hot percolation method for 72hr. After completion of the extraction the solvent was removed by using rotary evaporator. Thus the methanolic extract was obtained. The % yield was found to be 21.17% w/w. The extracts were preserved in a refrigerator for further study. The Methanolic (MEHI) extracts of *Helicteres isora* were subjected to the following investigations [13].

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The MEHI (Methanolic extraction of *Helicteres isora*) was screened for the presence of various phytoconstituents like carbohydrates, flavonoids, polyphenolic compounds, saponins, tannins, triterpenoids, etc [14, 15].

Estimation of *in-vitro* antioxidant activity

DPPH free radical scavenging activity

The scavenging reaction between (DPPH) and an antioxidant (H-A) was shown as below figure. 4.3 mg of DPPH (1, 1-Diphenyl –2-picrylhydrazyl) was dissolved in 3.3 ml methanol; it was protected from light by covering the test tubes with Aluminium foil. 150µl DPPH solutions were added to 3ml methanol and absorbance was taken immediately at 517nm for control reading. 25, 50, 75, 100 and 125 µg/ml of various concentrations of test (*Helicteres isora*) group compounds as well as standard compound (Ascorbic acid) were taken and the volume was made uniformly to 150 µl using methanol. Each of the samples was then further diluted with methanol up to 3ml and to each 150 µl DPPH was added [16].

(The concentrations were prepared as 1:1 ratio of test extract and DPPH in test group as well as Ascorbic acid and DPPH in Standard group). Absorbance was taken after 15 min. at 517nm using methanol as blank on UV-visible spectrometer Shimadzu, UV-1601, Japan. The IC50

values for each drug compounds as well as standard preparation were calculated. The DPPH free radical scavenging activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ scavenging} = \frac{[\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test sample}]}{[\text{Absorbance of control}]} \times 100$$

The effective concentration of sample required to scavenge DPPH radical by 50% (IC₅₀ value) was obtained by linear regression analysis of dose-response curve plotting between % inhibition and concentrations.

Nitric oxide (NO) free radical scavenging method

50 µl of each of the concentrations of test group (*Helicteres isora*) compounds previously dissolved in DMSO, as well as ascorbic acid (standard compound) were taken in separate tubes and the volume was uniformly made up to 150 µl with methanol. To each tube 2.0 ml of sodium nitroprusside (10mM) in phosphate buffer saline was added. The solutions were incubated at room temperature for 150 minutes. The similar procedure was repeated with methanol as blank which served as control. After the incubation, 5 ml of griess reagent was added to each tube including control. The absorbance of chromophore formed was measured at 546 nm on UV-visible spectrometer Shimadzu, UV-1601, Japan. Ascorbic acid was used as positive control. The IC₅₀ value for each test compound as well as standard preparation was calculated [17, 18].

$$\% \text{ scavenging} = \frac{[\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test sample}]}{[\text{Absorbance of control}]} \times 100$$

Reducing power method (RP)

2.5 mL of 0.2 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) and 2.5 mL of K₃Fe (CN)₆ (1% w/v) are added to 1.0 mL of sample dissolved in distilled water. The resulting mixture is incubated at 50⁰C for 20 min, followed by the addition of 2.5 mL of Trichloro acetic acid (10% w/v). The mixture is centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min to collect the upper layer of the solution (2.5 mL), mixed with distilled water (2.5 mL) and 0.5 mL of FeCl₃ (0.1%, w/v). The absorbance is then measured at 700 nm against blank sample [19].

Anti-diabetic activity

Animals

Male Wistar Albino rats (240±20gms) were procured and a total of 42 rats (n=42) were used for the experiment. They were divided into 7 groups of 6 animals each. They were randomly housed in standard polypropylene cages and maintained under the standard conditions: room

temperature (25±3) ° C, humidity 45%-55%, 12/12 hr light/dark cycle. They were fed with commercially available normal pellet diet and water was allowed *ad libitum*. The animals were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions atleast one week prior to the behavioral experiments. Each animal was used only once. The animal handling was performed according to the Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) guidelines. Animals used in this study were treated and cared for in accordance with the guidelines recommended by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of College. Out of 42 rats 36 rats were induced diabetes [20].

Acute oral toxicity studies

Acute toxicity study for the methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora* was done according to the OECD guidelines No: 423 and dose was selected for treatment.

The overnight fasted rats were divided into 4 groups, each group consisting of 3 female animals. The extracts were given in various doses (5, 50, 300, and 2000 mg/kg) by oral route. After administration of the extract, the animal were observed continuously for the first 2 hours and at 24 hrs to detect changes in behavioral responses and also for tremors, convulsion, salivation, diarrhea, lethargy, sleep, and coma and also were monitored up to 14 days for the toxic symptoms and mortality [21].

Induction of diabetes- Alloxan induced

Following an overnight fast, fasting blood glucose levels rats were determined, with freshly prepared Alloxan monohydrate (2% solution, dissolved in 0.9% sodium chloride) in a dose of 120mg/kg body weight. Animals were carefully observed for first 24 hours following the injection for any evidence of allergic reactions, behavioral changes, convulsions and hypoglycemic attacks. No untoward reaction was observed in any animal [22].

Grouping:

Group I: Served as normal control and did not receive any treatment.

Group II: Served as diabetic control and received alloxan (120 mg/kg) and vehicle.

Group III: Alloxan (120 mg/kg) + Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg p.o.) and served as standard.

Group IV: Alloxan (120 mg/kg) + MEHI extract (200 mg/kg, p.o.)

Group V: Alloxan (120 mg/kg) + MEHI extract (400 mg/kg, p.o.)

After 3 days (72 hours) of alloxan injection, the animals developed stable hyperglycemia. Only those animals with blood glucose level more than 250mg/dl were selected for the study. Later they were divided into five groups each comprising of 6 rats. Normal control, diabetic control

and standard groups kept same for anti-diabetic activity of plant extracts. The treatment (p. o.) was started from the same day except normal control and diabetic control groups for a period of 14 days. During this period, animals in all groups had free access to standard diet and water. Body weight and blood glucose levels were measured on '0' day, 3rd, 7th and 14th day of the post treatment in overnight fasted animals. On 3rd, 7th and 14th days, other biochemical parameters (SGOT, SGPT, Cholesterol and Triglycerides) were estimated in all animals.

Collection of blood:

The blood for the estimation was collected from the retro orbital plexus into the centrifuge vials. Later serum was separated by centrifugation of blood at a speed of 2000 rpm for 10 minutes. The serum was collected and quantitatively analyzed for blood glucose, triglycerides, cholesterol, SGOT (Serum glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase) and SGPT (Serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase) by using their respective kits.

Estimation of bio chemical parameters

Estimated different biochemical parameters like Glucose in serum [23], Serum Glutamate Oxaloacetate Transaminase levels (SGOT) [24], Serum Glutamate Pyruvate Transaminase levels (SGPT) [25], Cholesterol in serum [26], Triglycerides in serum [27]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary phytochemical screening:

Results of the preliminary phytochemical screening on methanolic leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* were shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Preliminary phytochemical screening

S. No.	Test	Methanolic extract
1.	Carbohydrates	+
2.	Proteins and Amino acids	+
3.	Tannins	+
4.	Flavonoids	+
5.	Steroids	+
6.	Cardiac glycosides	+
7.	Saponins	+

In-vitro* Anti-oxidant activity:*DPPH method:**

As the concentration of the drug increased, the % inhibition also increased. The highest % inhibition of Ascorbic acid (74.12 ± 0.93), MEHI (70.51 ± 0.95) was recorded at a concentration of $125 \mu\text{g/ml}$. IC_{50} and R^2 values were calculated. The antioxidant activity of MEHI is almost equal to that of the standard. The results were presented in **table 2 & 3; Figures 1 & 2**.

Nitric Oxide method:

As the concentration of the drug increased, the % inhibition also increased. The highest % inhibition of Ascorbic acid (92.82 ± 1.16), MEHI (72.01 ± 1.02) was recorded at a concentration of $125 \mu\text{g/ml}$. IC_{50} and R^2 values were calculated. The antioxidant activity of MEHI is almost equal to that of the standard. The results were presented in **table 4 & 5; Figure 3 & 4**.

Reducing Power Assay:

As the concentration of the drug increased, the antioxidant activity also increased. The antioxidant activity of MEHI is almost similar to that of the standard. The results were presented in **Table 6**.

Table 2: DPPH method of Ascorbic acid

Concentration	Log Concentration	%Inhibition	R^2 Value & IC_{50}
5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.698	12.62 ± 0.13	$\text{IC}_{50} = 58.498$ $R^2 = 0.9914$
10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	1.000	18.09 ± 0.14	
15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	1.176	24.56 ± 1.08	
25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	1.397	40.06 ± 0.16	
50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	1.698	55.65 ± 0.77	
75 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	1.875	66.52 ± 0.53	
100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	2.000	68.04 ± 0.57	
125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	2.096	72.12 ± 0.93	

Figure 1: DPPH method of Ascorbic acid

Table 3: DPPH Method of Methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora*

Concentration	Log concentration	%Inhibition	R^2 Value & IC ₅₀
5 µg/ml	0.698	10.60 ± 1.07	IC ₅₀ = 77.40 $R^2 = 0.9905$
10 µg/ml	1.000	15.06 ± 1.20	
15 µg/ml	1.176	22.92 ± 1.14	
25 µg/ml	1.397	39.90 ± 1.07	
50 µg/ml	1.698	52.51 ± 1.20	
75 µg/ml	1.875	58.74 ± 0.49	
100 µg/ml	2.000	62.54 ± 1.19	
125 µg/ml	2.096	70.51 ± 0.95	

Figure 2: DPPH method of methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora*

Table 4: Nitric Oxide method of Ascorbic acid

Concentration	Log concentration	%Inhibition (Mean \pm SEM)	R ² Value & IC ₅₀
5 μ g/ml	0.698	5.03 \pm 0.81	IC ₅₀ = 41.89 R ² = 0.9813
10 μ g/ml	1.000	12.12 \pm 1.25	
15 μ g/ml	1.176	24.81 \pm 0.67	
25 μ g/ml	1.397	43.33 \pm 1.09	
50 μ g/ml	1.698	68.28 \pm 1.46	
75 μ g/ml	1.875	78.56 \pm 0.74	
100 μ g/ml	2.000	80.23 \pm 1.21	
125 μ g/ml	2.096	88.82 \pm 1.16	

Figure 3: Nitric Oxide scavenging method of Ascorbic acid

Table 5: Nitric Oxide Method of Methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora*

Concentration	Log concentration	%Inhibition (Mean \pm SEM)	R ² Value & IC ₅₀
5 μ g/ml	0.698	4.42 \pm 0.94	IC ₅₀ = 78.65 R ² = 0.9869
10 μ g/ml	1.000	10.19 \pm 0.73	
15 μ g/ml	1.176	17.86 \pm 1.47	
25 μ g/ml	1.397	30.62 \pm 1.36	
50 μ g/ml	1.698	54.77 \pm 0.81	
75 μ g/ml	1.875	61.84 \pm 1.05	
100 μ g/ml	2.000	66.25 \pm 1.32	
125 μ g/ml	2.096	72.01 \pm 1.02	

Figure 4: Nitric Oxide method of methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora***Table 6: Reducing Power Assay**

Concentration (μ g/ml)	Absorbance at 700nm	
	Ascorbic Acid	Methanolic extract
25	0.34	0.31
50	0.62	0.44
75	0.85	0.76
100	0.98	0.95
125	1.24	1.06

Anti-diabetic study:**Acute oral toxicity studies:**

The methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) was found to be safe since no animal died even at the maximum dose of 2000 mg/kg when administered orally. Hence 1/5th, 1/10th dose of 2000 mg/kg were selected for the present study. i. e. 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg.

Effect of MEHI on Morphological parameters:**Effect on Body weight:**

In diabetic control group treated with alloxan (120 mg/kg, i. p, and single dose) a decrease in the body weights of animals on the 3rd, 7th and 14th day (224.1±3.99, 216.4±6.07 and 205.1±3.27) was observed when compared to the 0th day body weight (250.7±6.58). This indicates that alloxan reduced the body weights persistently.

The rats treated with methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) prevented reduction in body weights compared to diabetic control group. The MEHI effect on body weight data was presented in **Table 7**.

Table 7: Effect of MEHI on Body weights in Alloxan induced diabetic rats:

Treatment Group	Body weight of animals (g)			
	'0' day	3 rd day	7 th day	14 th day
Normal control	248.1±4.21	250.5±5.81	252.4±3.58	254.2±4.42
Diabetic control	250.7±6.58	224.1±3.99	216.4±6.07	205.1±3.27
Alloxan+ Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg)	246.4±5.40	218.4±6.09	224.5±4.58	232.5±5.06
Alloxan + MEHI (200 mg/kg)	244.2±4.76	216.6±2.74	221.6±2.86	230.3±7.19
Alloxan + MEHI (400 mg/kg)	245.3±5.29	226.4±7.68	230.3±6.97	237.5±2.77

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM for six animals

MEHI: Methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora*

Effect of MEHI on Biochemical parameters:**Effect on Serum Glucose levels:**

In diabetic control group treated with alloxan (120 mg/kg, single dose) a significant increase ($p < 0.001$) in the serum glucose levels on the 3rd, 7th and 14th day (290.07 ± 10.47 , 312.67 ± 11.04 and 348.14 ± 9.71) was observed when compared to the normal control group (84.68 ± 9.01 , 92.68 ± 7.00 and 95.81 ± 8.05) respectively. This indicates that alloxan induces persistent diabetes mellitus.

In the group receiving standard drug (Glibenclamide, 10 mg/kg, p. o, once daily) there was a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) in the serum glucose levels on the 3rd, 7th and 14th day (348.56 ± 8.26 , 250.44 ± 7.72 and 132.97 ± 6.84) respectively when compared to the diabetic control group. In standard group, the serum glucose levels decreased significantly by day 14.

On administration of methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora* (200mg/kg, p. o, once daily) there was a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in the serum glucose levels on 3rd, 7th and 14th day (361.61 ± 9.40 , 269.64 ± 9.29 and 157.23 ± 8.98) when compared to diabetic control group respectively. The other group receiving methanolic extract of *Helicteres isora* (400mg/kg, p. o, once daily) also showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) in serum glucose levels on 3rd, 7th and 14th day (378.84 ± 10.61 , 259.88 ± 8.03 and 145.59 ± 8.23) when compared to diabetic control group. A dose related decrease in serum glucose levels was observed in the MEHI (200mg/kg and 400mg/kg). This result suggests the anti-diabetic activity of *Helicteres isora*. The effect of MEHI on serum glucose levels was given in **Table 8**.

Effect on SGOT:

Rats treated with alloxan (diabetic control) showed a significant increase ($p < 0.001$) in SGOT levels (128.98 ± 6.112 , 138.09 ± 5.25 and 148.63 ± 5.48) when compared to normal control (54.07 ± 3.62 , 56.70 ± 4.15 and 56.34 ± 4.17) when measured on days 3rd, 7th and 14th.

The group treated with standard drug showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) in SGOT levels (151.41 ± 4.07 , 92.46 ± 3.50 and 71.105 ± 3.91) when compared to diabetic control.

The groups receiving methanolic leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) at doses of 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg, p. o, once daily) showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) in SGOT levels (159.45 ± 4.36 , 103.89 ± 4.25 and 92.46 ± 4.11) and (152.10 ± 3.82 , 98.46 ± 3.93 and 79.97 ± 4.89) when measured on days 3rd, 7th and 14th respectively when compared to diabetic control group.

Compared to 200 mg/kg dose, 400 mg/kg dose of MEHI has shown better reduction in the SGOT levels. Among the two extracts MEHI 400 mg/kg dose has shown still greater reduction which is almost similar to that of the standard. The effect of MEHI on serum SGOT was given in **Table 9**.

Effect on SGPT:

Rats treated with alloxan (diabetic control) showed a significant increase (0.001) in SGPT levels (74.67±5.60, 97.31±4.63 and 102.02±4.93) when compared to normal control (39.08±3.47, 39.88±3.82 and 37.54±3.32) when measured on days 3rd, 7th and 14th.

The group treated with standard drug showed a significant decrease ($p<0.01$) in SGPT levels (98.39±3.87, 61.5±3.46 and 51.63±3.21) when compared to diabetic control.

The groups treated with different doses of methanolic leaf extract of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) such as 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg showed a significant decrease ($p<0.01$) in SGPT levels (97.57±4.70, 73.51±3.76 and 72.74±4.82) and (106.68±4.01, 63.61±3.24 and 58.96±3.62) when measured on days 3rd, 7th and 14th respectively when compared to diabetic control group.

Compared to 200 mg/kg dose, 400 mg/kg dose of both the extracts (MEHI) has shown better reduction in the SGPT levels. Among the two extracts MEHI 400 mg/kg dose has shown still greater reduction which is almost similar to that of the standard. The effect of MEHI on serum SGPT was given in **Table 10**.

Effect on Serum cholesterol:

A significant increase in serum cholesterol ($p<0.001$) was observed in rats treated with alloxan (diabetic control) (122.33±5.16, 130.37±4.71 and 141.38±5.92) respectively when measured on days 3rd, 7th and 14th when compared to normal control (55.04±3.65, 54.02±3.18 and 55.88±4.51).

The group treated with standard drug (glibenclamide, 10mg/kg, p. o, once daily) showed a significant decrease in serum cholesterol levels (143.58±3.90, 101.26±3.57 and 79.66±4.25) when measured on days 3rd, 7th and 14th when compared to the diabetic control group.

The groups receiving methanolic leaf extract of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) at a dose of 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg showed a significant decrease ($p<0.01$) in serum cholesterol levels (142.01±4.69, 109.31±4.65 and 95.32±5.48) and (154.39±4.28, 102.60±3.26 and 88.17±4.82) respectively when compared to diabetic control group.

The serum cholesterol levels were decreased from day 3rd to day 14th in groups treated with standard drug, methanolic leaf extracts of HI. These values suggest that Glibenclamide, MEHI had cholesterol lowering activity.

Compared to 200 mg/kg dose, 400 mg/kg dose of extracts (MEHI) has shown better reduction in the cholesterol levels. Among the two extracts MEHI 400 mg/kg dose has shown still greater reduction which is almost similar to that of the standard. The effect of MEHI on serum cholesterol was given in **Table 11**.

Effect on serum triglycerides:

Rats treated with alloxan (diabetic control) showed a significant increase in ($p < 0.001$) serum TG levels on 3rd, 7th and 14th day (118.02 ± 5.09 , 139.64 ± 4.98 and 139.09 ± 3.98) respectively when compared to normal group (77.06 ± 4.00 , 78.14 ± 3.10 and 77.58 ± 2.51). The group treated with standard drug (Glibenclamide, 10mg/kg, p. o, once daily) had a triglyceride levels of (140.33 ± 3.91 , 100.18 ± 3.96 and 84.45 ± 3.41) when measured on days 3rd, 7th and 14th respectively. This was significantly lower ($p < 0.01$) when compared to diabetic control.

Diabetic rats treated with MEHI (200mg/kg, p. o, once daily) showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) in triglyceride levels on 3rd, 7th and 14th days (147.35 ± 5.27 , 115.92 ± 4.33 and 92.80 ± 3.16) when compared to the diabetic control respectively. The other group receiving high dose MEHI (400mg/kg) also showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) in serum TG on 3rd, 7th and 14th day (134.67 ± 3.95 , 110.33 ± 3.74 and 88.10 ± 2.79) when compared to diabetic group respectively.

These values suggest that Glibenclamide and MEHI had triglyceride lowering activity and the methanolic leaf extract 400mg/kg had exhibited almost similar effect on TG as that of glibenclamide.

Compared to 200 mg/kg dose, 400 mg/kg dose of both the extracts (MEHI) has shown better reduction in the triglyceride levels. Among the two extracts MEHI 400 mg/kg dose has shown still greater reduction which is almost similar to that of the standard. The effect of leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) on serum triglycerides was given in **Table 12**.

Table 8: Effect of MEHI on Blood Glucose levels in Alloxan induced diabetic rats

Treatment Group	Serum Glucose levels (mg/dL)			
	'0' day	3 rd day	7 th day	14 th day
Normal control	84.75±3.22	84.68±9.01	92.68±7.00	95.81±8.05
Diabetic control	90.24±2.70	290.07±10.47**	312.67±11.04**	348.14±9.71**
Alloxan + Glibenclamide (10mg/kg)	85.55±3.41	348.56±8.26**	250.44±7.72**	132.97±6.84**
Alloxan MEHI (200mg/kg)	84.81±3.81	361.61±9.40**	269.64±9.29**	157.23±8.98**
Alloxan + MEHI (400mg/kg)	78.51±2.63	378.84±10.61**	259.88±8.03**	145.59±8.23**

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM for six animals

*P < 0.05 and ** P < 0.01 Vs Diabetic control

MEHI: Methanolic Extract of *Helicteres isora*

Table 9: Effect of MEHI on Serum SGOT levels in Alloxan induced diabetic rats

Treatment Group	Serum SGOT (IU/L)		
	3 rd day	7 th day	14 th day
Normal control	54.07±3.62	56.70±4.15	56.34±4.17
Diabetic control	128.98±6.11**	138.09±5.25**	148.63±5.48**
Alloxan + Glibenclamide (10mg/kg)	151.41±4.07**	92.46±3.50**	71.105±3.91**
Alloxan + MEHI (200mg/kg)	159.45±4.36**	103.89±4.25**	92.46±4.11**
Alloxan + MEHI (400mg/kg)	152.10±3.82**	98.46±3.93**	79.97±4.89**

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM for six animals

*P < 0.05 and ** P < 0.01 Vs Diabetic control

MEHI: Methanolic Extract of *Helicteres isora*

Table 10: Effect of MEHI I on Serum SGPT levels in Alloxan induced diabetic rats

Treatment Group	SGPT levels		
	3 rd day	7 th day	14 th day
Normal control	39.08±3.47	39.88±3.82	37.54±3.32
Diabetic control	74.67±5.60**	97.31±4.63**	102.02±4.93**
Alloxan + Glibenclamide (10mg/kg)	98.39±3.87**	61.5±3.46**	51.63±3.21**
Alloxan + MEHI (200mg/kg)	97.57±4.70**	73.51±3.76**	72.74±4.82**
Alloxan + MEHI (400mg/kg)	106.68±4.01**	63.61±3.24**	58.96±3.62**

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM for six animals

*P < 0.05 and ** P < 0.01 Vs Diabetic control

MEHI: Methanolic Extract of *Helicteres isora*

Table 11: Effect of MEHI on Serum Cholesterol levels in Alloxan induced diabetic rats

Treatment Group	Serum Cholesterol (mg/dL)		
	3 rd day	7 th day	14 th day
Normal control	55.04±3.65	54.02±3.18	55.88±4.51
Diabetic control	122.33±5.16**	130.37±4.71**	141.38±5.92**
Alloxan + Glibenclamide (10mg/kg)	143.58±3.90**	101.26±3.57**	79.66±4.25**
Alloxan + MEHI(200mg/kg)	142.01±4.69*	109.31±4.65**	95.32±5.48**
Alloxan + MEHI (400mg/kg)	154.39±4.28**	102.60±3.26**	88.17±4.82**

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM for six animals

*P < 0.05 and ** P < 0.01 Vs Diabetic control

MEHI: Methanolic Extract of *Helicteres isora*

Table 12: Effect of MEHI on Serum Triglyceride levels in Alloxan induced diabetic rats

Treatment Group	Serum Triglycerides (mg/dL)		
	3 rd day	7 th day	14 th day
Normal control	77.06±4.00	78.14±3.10	77.58±2.51
Diabetic control	118.02±5.09**	139.64±4.98**	139.09±3.98**
Alloxan + Glibenclamide (10mg/kg)	140.33±3.91**	100.18±3.96**	84.45±3.41**
Alloxan + MEHI (200mg/kg)	147.35±5.27**	115.92±4.33**	92.80±3.16**
Alloxan + MEHI (400mg/kg)	134.67±3.95*	110.33±3.74**	88.10±2.79**

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM for six animals

*P < 0.05 and ** P < 0.01 Vs Diabetic control

MEHI: Methanolic Extract of *Helicteres isora*

DISCUSSION

Diabetes mellitus is a complex and a multifarious group of disorders that disturbs the metabolism of carbohydrates, fats and proteins. The prevalence of diabetes throughout the world has increased dramatically during the last few decades affecting nearly 10% of the population. Diabetes mellitus relates to the development of micro and macro vascular complications, which contribute greatly to the morbidity and mortality associated with the disease. There is a high level of treatment failures, unpleasant side effects and enormous cost associated with oral antidiabetic drugs generating an urgent need and desire for alternative treatments. In the last few years there has been an exponential growth in the field of herbal medicine and these drugs are gaining popularity both in developing and developed countries because of their natural origin and less side effects [28].

It is evident that no animal model is identical to any human syndrome. Among the available animal models of Type 2 diabetes mellitus, no model exactly stimulates the disease. For evaluating anti diabetic agents, alloxan rat model has several advantages over the other models like less cost and more reproducibility. Alloxan is a toxic glucose analogue which selectively destroys insulin-producing cells (beta cells) in the pancreas. When administered to rodents and

many other animal species liver glycogen depletes faster, severity of hypoglycemia is less and reversible action of alloxan can be seen only after three months, hence it is considered as one of the suitable experimental animal model for Type 2 diabetes mellitus. Alloxan, in the presence of intracellular thiols, generates reactive oxygen species (ROS) in a cyclic reaction with its reduction product, dialuric acid. The beta cell toxic action of alloxan is initiated by free radicals formed in the redox reaction.

In our study, administration of alloxan increased serum glucose levels when compared to normal animals and also induced persistent diabetes mellitus in rats. Similar effect of alloxan was also observed in reports observed on *Phyllanthus amarus* and *Artemisia judaica* [29, 30].

In the present study, the standard drug used was glibenclamide. It belongs to the second generation sulphonyl ureas and works by inhibiting the sulfonylurea receptor 1, the regulatory subunit of ATP-sensitive potassium channels in pancreatic β cells. This inhibition causes cell membrane depolarization opening voltage dependent calcium channel. This results in an increase in intracellular calcium in the beta cell and subsequent stimulation of insulin release. Our results showed that glibenclamide reduced blood glucose levels in hyperglycemic animals; the state of diabetes is not severe. This reduction in serum glucose was similar to earlier reports observed with *Costus pictus*, *Michelia champaca* and *Phyllanthus emblica* [31, 32].

In the present study, the plant drug used is leaves of *Helicteres isora*. The result of phytochemical screening on the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) revealed the presence of various pharmacologically active compounds such as tannins and flavonoids.

The alloxan treated diabetic, rats receiving leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg showed rapid normalization of blood glucose levels in comparison to diabetic control and this could be due to possibility that some β cells are still surviving to act upon by *Helicteres isora* to exert its insulin releasing effect. Dose dependent reduction in blood glucose was also observed. This effect observed was similar to the effect observed with *Michelia champaca* and *Costus igneus* in alloxan induced diabetic rats [33].

In our study, assay of liver enzymes SGOT and SGPT indicates a decrease in their activities in both glibenclamide and leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) treated groups. Increase in these liver enzymes is an indication of liver damage and so from the results obtained in this study, the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) and glibenclamide had protective effects on the liver.

These reductions in liver enzymes were similar to earlier reports observed with *Ichnocarpus frutescens* [34].

In the present study, serum cholesterol concentrations following the treatment with glibenclamide and leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) were found decreased when compared to diabetic group. High cholesterol levels are associated with coronary artery disease (CAD) observed in diabetic patients. The decrease in serum cholesterol was also reported with other plants *Artemisia judaica*, *Costus pictus* and *Michelia champaca* [35].

In our investigation, decrease in the levels of serum triglycerides was observed in glibenclamide and leaf extracts (MEHI) treated groups when compared to diabetic group. This reduction in serum triglycerides was also observed while evaluating anti-diabetic activity of other plant drugs such as *Cassia occidentalis* and *Artemisia judaica* [36].

Oxidative stress is the state in which the level of toxic reactive oxygen intermediates (ROI) overcomes the endogenous antioxidant defences of the host which occurs at an early stage in diabetes. Hyperglycemia aggravates endothelial ROS generation by a variety of mechanisms such as activation of protein kinase-C isoform, increased formation of advanced glycation end products and increased glucose flux through aldose reductase pathways. These are some of the known biochemical mechanisms of hyperglycemia-induced tissue/organ damage.

Reactive species can be eliminated by a number of enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants and thus protecting tissue/organ damage from oxidative stress. In the present study, we estimated both enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants in pancreas *in vivo*.

Malondialdehyde (MDA) is an end product of lipid peroxidation, a non-enzymatic antioxidant; present in less concentration scavenges hydroxyl free radicals. In our study, increase in MDA was observed in diabetic rats than in the group treated with glibenclamide and leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI). This shows that leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* has an antioxidant property. The results were similar to the reports observed with *Cassia tora* [37].

Glutathione is an enzymatic antioxidant. Glutathione peroxidase, a selenium containing enzyme when present in significant concentrations detoxifies H_2O_2 to H_2O through the oxidation of reduced glutathione. In the present study, decrease in reduced glutathione activity, observed in diabetic rats has been shown to be an important adaptive response to increased oxidative stress. The increased activity of reduced glutathione observed in diabetic rats treated with glibenclamide

and leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) indicates that these extracts have an antioxidant activity. The results were similar to the reports observed with *Moringa oleifera* [38].

Catalase is an enzymatic antioxidant. Catalase is a haemprotein which catalyses the reduction of hydrogen peroxide and protects the tissue from highly reactive hydroxyl radicals. In our study, the reduced activity of catalase in pancreas was observed during diabetes may result in deleterious effects due to accumulation of superoxide anion radicals and hydrogen peroxide. The increased activity of catalase was observed in alloxan-induced diabetic rats treated with glibenclamide and leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) indicating that these extracts possess antioxidant property. The results were similar to reports observed with *Oscillatoria annae* [39].

In our investigations, the levels of enzymatic antioxidants (catalase, reduced GSH) declined in diabetic animals were significantly restored on treatment with leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI). The levels of non-enzymatic antioxidant (MDA) increased in diabetic animals, were significantly decreased in diabetic animals treated with glibenclamide and leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI). This implies that the potential antioxidant defence is reactivated by the active principles of *Helicteres isora*, with an increase in the capacity for detoxification through enhanced scavenging of oxy radicals.

In the present study, in vitro antioxidant studies were also carried out to assess scavenging potential of *Helicteres isora*. DPPH is the most widely reported method for screening of antioxidant activity of many plant drugs. This method is based on the reduction of methanolic solution of colored free radical DPPH by free radical scavenger. The procedure involves measurement of decrease in absorbance of DPPH at its absorption maxima of 516 nm, which is proportional to concentration of free radical scavenger added to DPPH reagent solution. From the results of the present study, it may be postulated that active principles in the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) have hydrogen donors thus scavenging the free radicals. The results were similar to earlier reports observed with *Baccopa monnieri* and *Centella asiatica* [40].

Nitric oxide, because of its unpaired electron, is classified as a free radical and displays important reactivity's with certain types of proteins and other free radicals. In vitro inhibition of nitric oxide radical is also a measure of antioxidant activity. In the present study, the nitrite produced by the incubation of solutions of sodium nitroprusside in standard phosphate buffer at 25°C was reduced by the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI). This may be due to the antioxidant principles in the leaf extracts, which compete with oxygen to react with nitric oxide

there by inhibiting the generation of nitrite. In the present study, the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) has inhibition but less than ascorbic acid in scavenging NO. The results obtained were similar to that reports observed with *Acalypha Indica* [41].

Reducing power assay is based on the principle of increase in the absorbance of the reaction mixture. Increase in the absorbance indicates increase in the antioxidant activity. The leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) reacted with potassium ferricyanide (Fe³⁺) to form potassium ferrocyanide (Fe²⁺), which then reacted with ferric chloride to form ferric ferrous complex that has an absorption maximum at 700 nm. This may be due to the antioxidant principles in the leaf extracts. In the present study, the leaf extract of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) has antioxidant activity almost equal to that of the ascorbic acid. The results were similar to the earlier reports observed with *Gymnema sylvestre* [42].

From these results, it is proved that the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) has an anti-diabetic and antioxidant activity. These results thus support the claim of use of this plant in diabetic conditions.

Further work is obviously required to fractionate, purify, identify and to elucidate the exact mechanism of action of the hypoglycaemic principles present in the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI).

CONCLUSION

Diabetes mellitus is a group of syndromes characterized by hyperglycemia, altered metabolism of lipids, carbohydrates and proteins, and an increased risk of complications from vascular disease. Herbal medicine is gaining popularity because of their natural origin and less side effects. Development and utilization of anti-diabetic plants have attracted increasing interest.

Plants contain a wide array of free radical scavenging molecules which possess both hypoglycemic and antioxidant activities. So, the present study was planned to evaluate the leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* for its antidiabetic and antioxidant activities.

Hypoglycemic activity was evaluated by using alloxan-induced diabetic rat model in which the rats were treated with alloxan (120 mg/kg).

In the present study, the parameters monitored were serum glucose, triglycerides, cholesterol, SGOT, SGPT, *in vitro* antioxidant parameters (NO scavenging, DPPH and Reducing power).

The present study clearly indicated a significant anti-diabetic activity with the Methanolic leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* (MEHI) and supports the traditional usage of leaves by the

Ayurvedic physicians for the control of diabetes. Hence, it was concluded that the leaf extracts have anti-diabetic activity. The phytochemicals like tannins, flavonoids present in the extracts may be responsible for anti-diabetic activity. The leaf extracts of *Helicteres isora* also showed a significant antioxidant activity; hence it might help in preventing diabetic complications.

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